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2nd International Conference on
**Transforming Innovation in
Agriculture, Environment and
Health for Sustainable
Development**

07th -08th September, 2024

SOUVENIR
Cum **ABSTRACT**
Book

Editors

Dr. Yogesh K. Agarwal

Dr. U. K. Singh

Dr. Hemant Kumar

Dr. Manish Kumar

Dr. Gaurav Agarwal

Co-Editors

Dr. Anil Kumar

Dr. Vipin Mishra

AgriLife 2024

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NESTING BEHAVIOR OF CROCODYLUS PALUSTRIS AND POTENTIAL SURVIVAL ADVANTAGES LINKED TO DIFFERENT NEST STRUCTURES IN A SANCTUARY PREMISES IN HARYANA, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The present studies endeavour to focus attention on the Tunnel behavior of Indian Marsh Mugger in “Bhor Saidan Crocodile Sanctuary” in Kurukshetra district of Haryana state in India. The Sanctuary premises are spread over an area of about 25-30 Acres with a good marshy land. The marsh mugger (*Crocodylus palustris*), also known as the mugger crocodile or the broad-snouted crocodile, is a species of crocodylian native to the Indian subcontinent. An extensive one-year study identified four distinct types of crocodile nests, each with unique features and specific functions. These nests were categorized as Funnel Nests, Simple Tunnel Nests, Chamber Nests, and Tunnel Nests with Doorsills. Each type served a different purpose: Funnel Nests were primarily used by adult crocodiles for resting, while Chamber Nests were utilized for egg laying. The Tunnel Nest with a Doorsill provided a dual function, offering a hiding place for hatchlings in their early days and preventing water from entering the nest hole. The study extensively examined nesting behavior and recorded physical parameters such as ambient temperature and humidity, correlating these factors with the nest architecture. The findings indicated that the choice of nest site and type significantly impacts the species' survival.

KEYWORDS: *Crocodylus palustris*, marshy land, Funnel Nests, Tunnel Nest

CHANGES IN THE BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF DROUGHT

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ABSTRACT

Through this thesis, we got acquainted with many scientific works on the change of biological properties of soils under the influence of drought, which is a part of our research. Studies and related meta-analyses on drought stress in soils have often shown a deleterious effect of drought on the diversity and abundance of soil microbial communities, particularly in soil bacterial development. Can be observed. Arid regions are increasing year by year, but their microbiological diversity is still poorly characterized. The microbiome is an important component of the soil ecosystem, as soil microorganisms are more involved in providing a source of nutrients for total biomass production than plants and animals. The microbiome is an important component of the soil ecosystem, as soil microorganisms contribute more to the total biomass production than plants and animals in providing a source of nutrients. As we all know, microorganisms produce

many secretions. These extracts, i.e. enzymes, have a positive effect on various properties of the soil and improve metabolism. Cyclic cycling of nutrients in soils is highly dependent on extracellular enzymes. In this case, enzymes are produced by soil microbes through the decomposition of complex organic matter, polymeric carbon and nitrogenous substrates (eg, lignin, cellulose, pectin, hemicellulose and microbial residues). These products ultimately lead to microbial metabolism and are beneficial for plant growth. A decrease in urease activity was also confirmed with a decrease in the level of soil moisture due to the drying factor. We know that urease is one of the most important soil enzymes in the nitrogen cycle. There are many ways to reduce the negative effects of drought. In particular, it is necessary to add additives to the soil, to increase the enzyme activity of the soil by adding various types of organic matter, i.e. biochar, compost, sewage sludge and biopreparations with different composition, to create additional alternative conditions for the microbiome, and it is possible to ensure that plants grow quickly by adapting to adverse conditions. The variety of microorganisms adapted to arid and desert regions is very large, and it was found that they consist of microorganisms that can withstand harsh environmental conditions. A studying and breeding microbiome community that are resistant to long-term abiotic stress such as water limitation and salt accumulation is important in arid lands.

KEYWORDS: drought; microorganisms; soil properties; soil enzymes; soil fertility.

ISOLATION OF ENDOPHYTIC FUNGI FROM DIFFERENT ORGANS OF SAFFRON (*CROCUS SATIVUS*) PLANT AND DETERMINATION OF THEIR ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY
Raxmonova Mahbuba Ilhom qizi¹, No'monjon Sultanov Nabi o'g'li², Abdusamatov Soxibjon Abdusamatovich³ and Jabborova Dilfuza Pushkinovna⁴

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ABSTRACT

Crocus sativus is one of the important plants used in folk medicine since ancient times. Its various organs are considered to be one of the best tools in the fight against various diseases spread among people. Currently, saffron cultivation in Uzbekistan is facing various difficulties caused by various biotic and abiotic influences. It is known from previous researches that beneficial fungi and bacteria living in symbiosis with the plant have been found in various organs of the saffron plant. Endophytes are known to fight many diseases of their host plants. Endophytic plant microorganisms are a source of secondary metabolites in addition to the metabolites produced by the plant itself

We isolated endophytic fungi from different organs of the saffron plant, which we selected as the research object. For this purpose, Saburo, potato dextrose agar and Chapek nutrient media for fungi were prepared and sterilized and poured into Petri dishes. The outer surface of saffron plant organs such as roots, bulbs, leaves and stems were cleaned of epiphytic microorganisms and planted in nutrient media. Planted samples were incubated in a thermostat at 20 °C for 1

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